

Bhramari Pranayama Triggers Rapid Autonomic Shifts and Blood Pressure Reduction in Yoga-Naïve Young Adults

Running Title: Immediate Autonomic Effects of Bhramari Breathing

Names of the authors: Anushree Rai ¹, Hirok Chakraborty^{2*}, Vinay AV³, Sindhu R⁴,
Ratnesh Sinha⁵

Affiliation of authors:

1. MBBS Student, Manipal Tata Medical College, Jamshedpur, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India. ORCID: 0009-0002-4158-9424
2. MD Physiology, Department of Physiology, Manipal Tata Medical College, Jamshedpur, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India. ORCID: 0000-0002-6439-6599
3. MD Physiology, Department of Physiology, Manipal Tata Medical College, Jamshedpur, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India. ORCID: 0000-0002-9966-6931
4. MD Physiology, Department of Physiology, Manipal Tata Medical College, Jamshedpur, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, India. ORCID: 0009-0006-2125-3826
5. MD Community Medicine, Department of Community Medicine, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Ranchi, Jharkhanf, India. ORCID: 0000-0003-1788-5952

Name and postal address of the corresponding author:

Dr. Hirok Chakraborty, Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Manipal Tata Medical College, Kadani Road, Baridih, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand-831017

Abstract

Background:

Bhramari Pranayama (Bhpr), commonly known as “humming bee breath” is a yogic breathing technique that emphasizes slow, prolonged breathing accompanied by an audible humming sound. Although its calming effects are well recognized, quantitative evidence on its immediate autonomic and haemodynamic effects in yoga-naïve individuals remains limited. The present investigated the immediate effects of a single session of Bhpr on blood pressure (B.P) and heart rate variability (HRV) in healthy young adults without prior yoga experience.

Materials and Methods:

Seventy-three healthy yoga-naïve volunteers aged 20-35 years participated in the pre-post prospective study. Lead II ECG was recorded before and after a standardized 15-minute Bhpr session using an RMS digital polygraph. HRV was analyzed using standard time domain (SDNN, RMSSD, NN50, pNN50) and frequency domain (LF, HF, LF/HF ratio) parameters. B.P was measured before and after the session. Data were tested for normality and paired sample t- tests were applied. A p value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results: Compared with baseline, systolic B.P reduced significantly from 120.4 ± 9.31 to 115.8 ± 8.01 mmHg. Time domain HRV indices showed significant increase (SDNN: 67.00 ± 6.06 to 69.50 ± 4.99 ms, RMSSD 40.13 ± 16.27 to 50.33 ± 15.77 ms). Frequency-domain analysis revealed higher HF power with concomitant reductions in LF nu and LF/HF ratio. VLF% and LF% showed no significant change.

Conclusion: A brief 15-minute session of Bhpr elicited significant autonomic and cardiovascular benefits, evidenced by reduced systolic blood pressure and enhanced parasympathetic modulation across both time and frequency domain HRV indices. These findings support Bhpr as a rapid and effective practice for improving short-term autonomic regulation and cardiovascular stability.

Keywords: Bhramari Pranayama, Yoga, Heart Rate Variability, Blood Pressure, Parasympathetic Dominance.

Introduction:

The various breathing techniques which form an essential component of yoga are collectively termed as pranayama. Among the various pranayama, Bhramari Pranayama (Bhpr) is one of the simplest of all and is characterized by slow deep inhalation followed by a humming exhalation and has been conventionally considered as a method that promotes calmness and mental clarity (Shetty et al., 2024; Ushamohan et al., 2023). The humming thus produced generates subtle vibrations in the nasal and paranasal sinuses, that are believed to stimulate vagal afferents and promote parasympathetic activation (Chetry et al., 2024; Trivedi et al., 2023). Additionally, the controlled respiratory pattern observed in Bhpr can alter the autonomic outflow by modulating vagal afferents, baroreflex sensitivity, and cardiorespiratory synchronization (Sevoz-Couche & Laborde, 2022).

Heart rate variability (HRV) is a well-established, non-invasive marker of autonomic nervous system function (Malik, 1996). Higher HRV generally reflects greater parasympathetic (vagal) activity and autonomic flexibility, whereas reduced HRV is associated with stress, cardiovascular risk, and diminished adaptability (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017; Thayer et al., 2012). Slow and mindful breathing practices are known to enhance parasympathetic modulation, leading to improved HRV and reduced blood pressure (BP). (Kuppusamy et al., 2020; Sevoz-Couche & Laborde, 2022)

Preliminary studies have reported that even a brief Bhpr practice session of 5 minutes can reduce the heart rate (HR) and BP, along with favourable shift in HRV indices (Kuppusamy et al., 2016; Telles et al., 2012).

Although these findings underscore Bhpr's potential as a quick and accessible autonomic modulation technique, several limitations in the existing literature like breathing duration, training level etc restrict the extent to which these findings can be generalized (Laborde et al., 2022).

In long term interventions (Sharma et al., 2022) cumulative practice over weeks or months may obscure the acute effects of a single Bhpr session. Evaluating immediate Bhpr effects in yoga naïve individuals is particularly important, as it better reflects the physiological baseline of the general population and avoids confounding from prior habituation.

Earlier reviews (Kuppusamy et al., 2020; Saoji et al., 2019), indicate that research on Bhpr has largely involved trained yoga practitioner (Mooventhan & Khode, 2014; Telles et al.,

2012), and few studies have examined the combined influence of its distinctive features -slow breathing, humming exhalation and nasal closure (Sanmukha Mudra) in yoga naïve individuals (Kuppusamy et al., 2020).

The humming component of Bhpr is thought to increase the nasal nitric oxide concentration, aiding vasodilation and oxygen uptake (Lundberg et al., 1996). In addition, mild auditory and vibratory stimulation may attenuate cortical arousal and sympathetic drive, encouraging a state of relaxation (Jerath et al., 2006; Lundberg et al., 1996)

To address these gaps, the present study was designed to evaluate the immediate autonomic and hemodynamic effects of a single session of Bhpr in healthy, yoga naïve young adults. By addressing key methodological limitations of previous research, it aims to provide a clearer understanding of Bhpr's acute autonomic and cardiovascular effects and support its integration into clinical and preventive strategies.

Materials and Methods:

The study was conducted over six months in the Department of Physiology at a private medical college, in the eastern part of India, following approval from the institutional ethical committee (IEC). All volunteers provided written informed consent and procedures conformed to the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) guidelines,(Behera et al., 2019) and the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments. (Hellmann et al., 2024) Volunteers were recruited from the college's working population through open invitation. Inclusion criteria comprised physically healthy individuals aged 20-35 years with no prior experience of yoga or breathing practices. Exclusion criteria included regular yoga practitioners, individuals with chronic diseases (e.g.: hypertension, diabetes, chronic infections), those taking antipsychotic medication, and persons with a history of smoking, alcohol dependence or substance abuse.

A sample size of 73 was calculated using the online "Statulator" calculator (Singh, 2014), based on a mean difference of 3 units, a standard deviation of 9, a 90% confidence interval, 80% power, and Type I and II error rates of 5% and 20% respectively.

Tools used:

Anthropometric and demographic data were collected along with responses from a self-administered questionnaire that gathered information on medical history, chronic conditions, allergies, substance abuse and other relevant factors. A digital sphygmomanometer, model no: BPDG041 by "Diamond" recorded blood pressure. Height (in centimeters-cm) was measured using a wall-mounted measuring tape. The weight of the volunteers was documented using a

digital weighing scale (in Kilograms-kg) whereas the RMS (India) digital polygraph recorded the lead II ECG of the volunteer.

Study procedure description:

Seventy-three healthy volunteers (20-35 years, both sexes), reported to the department laboratory at about 08:00 a.m., following an overnight sound sleep of 8-10 hours and a light breakfast consumed at least two hours prior, without tea or coffee. After eligibility screening and obtaining informed consent, ECG leads were attached to the selected volunteers. A certified yoga trainer then demonstrated the Bhpr procedure as outlined below.

Bhpr procedure:

Volunteers were instructed to sit in an upright, comfortable position with eyes closed. Each volunteer placed their right thumb on the right external auditory canal (EAC) and left thumb on left EAC. The index and middle fingers together were positioned over closed eyelids, while the ring fingers of each hand rested on the same side of the nose. Volunteers were trained to inhale slowly through both nostrils to their maximum capacity and exhale gradually out through both nostrils. During exhalation, they were directed to chant " O-U-Mmma" while producing a buzzing nasal sound resembling the noise of a humming wasp (Kuppusamy et al., 2020)

Before recordings commenced, volunteers performed 2-3 practice trials of Bhpr. They were then told to sit relaxed with their eyes closed, avoiding sleep, while ECG recording was initiated using the polygraph machine. A 15-minute baseline ECG was recorded prior to Bhpr practice, followed by a 15-minute ECG recording immediately post intervention. The ECG leads remained attached throughout the process and were removed only after all the recordings were completed.

Step1: ECG leads attached - baseline ECG recording before Bhpr for 15 mins

Step2: Bhpr for 15 mins-ECG leads remain attached

Step 3: Post-Bhpr ECG recorded for 15 mins and then the leads were removed

Blood pressure was measured twice: once at the baseline (immediately before ECG recording) and again 15 minutes after Bhpr session (just after ECG record completion).

After the procedure volunteers remained seated in the laboratory for 20 minutes to observe and report any post-procedure effects.

ECG & HRV Data acquisition: HRV was computed from Lead II ECG recordings in accordance with the Task Force Guidelines. (Malik, 1996) All recordings were analyzed by RMS Vagus HRV software (RMS, India) which derives time and frequency domain HRV parameters after applying Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) to the ECG data.

At rest, parasympathetic activity is predominantly assessed through time domain HRV indices. Common measures include:

-**SDNN:** standard deviation of all normal-to-normal intervals

-**RMSSD:** root mean square of successive differences of intervals (RMSSD),

-**NN50:** pairs of successive normal-to-normal intervals differing by ≥ 50 milliseconds (Tyagi & Cohen, 2016)

Frequency domain analysis provides insight into autonomic balance by decomposing R-R intervals into spectral components of different frequencies. (Nivethitha et al., 2017) Power spectrum analysis by FFT permits the categorisation of HRV into 3 frequency bands:

-Very low frequency (**VLF**): < 0.04 Hz

-Low frequency (**LF**): 0.04–0.15 Hz, and

-High frequency (**HF**): 0.15–0.4 Hz respectively.

To account for inter-individual variability, LF and HF components were also expressed in normalized units (n.u.), such as HF n.u. and LF n.u, which represent relative contributions of each band to total power (Rajendra Acharya et al., 2006). All recordings were completed in a single visit on the same day.

Statistical analysis: Statistical analyses were performed using Jamovi software (version: 2.3.13). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Normality of pre–post difference scores was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test to confirm assumptions for parametric testing. Paired sample t-tests were applied to evaluate changes in BP and HRV parameters before and after Bhpr. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Out of the 90 screened volunteers, 73 met the inclusion and exclusion criteria and completed the study. Of the 73 volunteers who participated in the study, 46 were females and 27 were males. **Table 1** summarizes the demographic characteristics of the study participants including age, height, weight and BMI.

Table 1: Mean age, height, weight and BMI of the study population (N=73)

Parameters	Mean ± SD
Age (years)	21.4 ± 0.9
Height (m)	1.7 ± 0.1
Weight (kg)	68.5 ± 13.4
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.6 ± 4.4

Fig 1: Comparison of cardiovascular parameters (Systolic Blood Pressure and Diastolic Blood Pressure) in the study group, pre and post Bhpr for a sample size of N=73. Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation.

Paired 't' test, p-value <0.05 was taken as significant.

Comparison of systolic and diastolic blood pressure values (mean ± SD) before and after Bhpr are shown in **Fig1**. A paired t-test was used to find changes in cardiovascular parameters due to Bhpr. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) significantly reduced from 120.4 ± 9.31 mmHg to 115.8 ± 8.01 mmHg (p < **0.01***) after performing Bhpr. The diastolic blood pressure (DBP) did not reveal any significant variation; although a decreasing trend was observed (70.6 ± 7.79 mmHg to 69.8 ± 7.47 mmHg, p=0.178).

Table 2 presents the comparative HRV values (Mean \pm SD) before and after the performance of Bhpr.

Table 2: HRV parameters of the volunteers (N=73)

Parameter	Pre Bhpr (Mean \pm SD)	Post Bhpr (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
SDNN (ms)	67.00 \pm 6.06	69.50 \pm 4.99	0.004
RMSSD (ms)	40.13 \pm 16.27	50.33 \pm 15.77	< 0.001
NN50	156.19 \pm 50.48	186.59 \pm 63.68	< 0.001
pNN50	28.6 \pm 2.84	29.1 \pm 3.03	0.001
Variance	3991.99 \pm 1989.09	4537.63 \pm 2105.25	0.006
VLF %	58.05 \pm 13.77	58.99 \pm 16.75	0.712
LF %	26.61 \pm 7.11	25.28 \pm 7.68	0.236
HF %	16.50 \pm 4.95	18.33 \pm 6.05	0.044
LFnu	69.16 \pm 7.98	65.99 \pm 8.06	0.007
HFnu	35.51 \pm 6.85	41.40 \pm 6.79	< 0.001
VLF (ms²)	3453.88 \pm 1675.45	3410.94 \pm 1526.05	0.836
LF (ms²)	967.20 \pm 103.07	941.48 \pm 117.76	0.075
HF (ms²)	385.26 \pm 112.50	443.16 \pm 119.62	< 0.001
LF/HF Ratio	2.73 \pm 0.87	2.30 \pm 0.75	< 0.001

Paired 't' test, SDNN- standard deviation of RR Intervals adjacent normal-to-normal (NN) intervals in pre and post-performance of Bhpr; RMSSD- root mean square of differences between successive rhythm-to-rhythm (RR) intervals; NN50- pairs of successive normal-to-normal intervals that vary by ≥ 50 milliseconds; LF nu-low frequency normalized unit; HF-high frequency normalized unit; HR-heart rate; bpm-beats per minute; p-value < 0.05 was taken as significant in bold.

Paired-sample t tests revealed significant improvements in several time-domain HRV indices following Bhpr. As shown in the table, SDNN increased from 67.00 ± 6.06 to 69.50 ± 4.99 , RMSSD from 40.13 ± 16.27 to 50.33 ± 15.77 , NN50 from 156.19 ± 50.48 to 186.59 ± 63.68 and pNN50 from 28.6 ± 2.84 to 29.1 ± 3.03 . Variance also showed a significant rise, increasing from 3991.99 ± 1989.09 to 4537.63 ± 2105.25 .

For frequency-domain parameters, HF (%) increased from 16.50 ± 4.95 to 18.33 ± 6.05 , HF nu from 35.51 ± 6.85 to 41.40 ± 6.79 , HF (ms²) from 385.26 ± 112.50 to 443.16 ± 119.62 . Correspondingly, LF nu decreased from 69.16 ± 7.98 to 65.99 ± 8.06 and the LF/HF ratio declined from 2.73 ± 0.87 to 2.30 ± 0.75 . Other indices, including VLF%, LF%, VLF and LF (ms²) did not show statistically significant changes.

Normality of pre-post difference scores was confirmed using the Shapiro–Wilk test, fulfilling the assumption for paired-samples t-tests. Although some raw HRV variables displayed non-normal distributions, this does not violate statistical assumptions because normality of residuals, not raw values, is required for paired t-test. Additionally, the paired t-test is robust in large samples (N=73).

Discussion:

In this study, we evaluated the immediate cardiovascular and autonomic effects of a single 15-minute Bhramari Pranayama (Bhpr) session in healthy, yoga naïve young adults. The study demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in SBP along with notable improvements across multiple domains of HRV following a single Bhpr session. All these findings point towards the rapid shift of cardiac autonomic regulatory balance towards the parasympathetic system. The increase in time domain indices namely SDNN, RMSSD, NN50, pNN50 suggest enhanced beat-to-beat variability and greater parasympathetic control (Laborde et al., 2017; Shaffer et al., 2014). Complementary changes in frequency-domain markers, including higher HF power and a marked reduction in LF nu and the LF/HF ratio, suggest a reduced sympathetic activity (Goldstein et al., 2011). These alterations in HRV parameters may help explain the associated reduction in SBP, indicating greater autonomic adaptability and improved cardiovascular balance.

Blood pressure responses:

Our results are consistent with the reports by Nivethitha et al. (Nivethitha et al., 2017) and Sathe et al. (Sathe et al., 2020) which documented significant reductions of SBP after short Bhpr sessions. This response may be driven by reduced sympathetic tone, potentially associated with lower circulating catecholamines, as suggested in earlier studies on slow breathing practices (Gobel et al., 1978). DBP remained unchanged before and after Bhpr, suggesting that Bhpr may not substantially influence the peripheral vascular resistance, which is predominantly regulated by the sympathetic nervous system. This contrasts with the results of Pramanik et al., (Pramanik et al., 2010) who reported an increase in DBP, which may be due to differences in protocol duration or participant profiles.

Time domain parameters of HRV

SDNN, a key time domain index reflecting overall HRV and representing combined influence of both sympathetic and parasympathetic system (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017) significantly increased after 15 minutes of Bhpr. This global rise in HRV reflects improved autonomic flexibility, enabling ANS to adapt to widespread physiological variations without marked increase in HR. Similar observations were reported by Muralikrishnan et al. (Muralikrishnan et al., 2012) and Vinay et al. (Vinay et al., 2016) who observed improved sympathovagal balance following short-term yoga practice, reflecting modest gains in overall HRV.

The observed elevation in RMSSD, NN50 and pNN50 following Bhpr indicates increased vagal mediated parasympathetic activity. RMSSD, the primary measure of cardiac vagal tone (Aftyka et al., 2023) rose significantly in this study indicating enhancement of parasympathetic system in regulating cardiac activity. Our observations corroborate recent HRV findings, suggesting that even short duration breathing practices can rapidly improve parasympathetic tone and promote autonomic balance (Sevoz-Couche & Laborde, 2022). Prior work on controlled breathing and mind body interventions similarly reported increase in RMSSD and related HRV parameters, reflecting rapid vagal activity (Blaser et al., 2023; Laborde et al., 2017). The increase in NN50 and pNN50 further reinforces this interpretation by displaying longer inter-beat intervals and greater beat-to-beat variability, both markers of enhanced vagal tone (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017). Together these findings suggest that Bhpr may induce an immediate shift in cardiac autonomic regulation toward parasympathetic predominance.

These autonomic changes carry important implications, as higher HRV is linked to improved emotional control, better cognitive efficiency, and greater cardiovascular stability (McCraty & Shaffer, 2015). Accordingly, our findings suggest that even a short Bhpr session may facilitate physiological recovery and contribute to stress modulation.

Frequency domain parameters of HRV

The rise in HF power and HF nu, together with reductions in LF nu and the LF/HF ratio, indicates a shift towards the parasympathetic dominance after Bhpr. Heightened HF activity reflects stronger vagal influence on respiratory sinus arrhythmia, suggesting enhanced autonomic elasticity (Arakaki et al., 2023). Likewise the concurrent decline in LF nu and LF/HF ratio highlights a reduction in sympathetic drive and overall improvement in sympathovagal balance (Billman, 2013).

These findings align with recent evidence highlighting that slow, rhythmic breathing and yogic practices rapidly augment HF power by stimulating vagal pathways and promoting baroreflex function (Laborde et al., 2022). Furthermore, a recent systematic review reported that mind-body and breath-regulation techniques consistently boost parasympathetic mediated frequency domain indices particularly HF nu while reducing LF/HF ratio, thereby improving autonomic regulation (Sujie et al., 2024). Emerging evidence suggests that acute increases in HF power serve as a reliable marker of enhanced physiology recovery, stress reduction and emotional self-regulation capacity (Shaffer & Ginsberg, 2017). Strengthened vagal engagement has been associated with improved prefrontal regulatory function, reduced inflammatory signalling and better cardiovascular stability (Arakaki et al., 2023).

Therefore, the frequency domain changes observed after Bhpr may not only reflect short term autonomic adjustments but carry implications for long term autonomic cardiovascular balance. Our findings demonstrate the capacity of Bhpr to produce rapid, favourable shifts in autonomic tone. These effects were evident in individuals without prior yoga experience, reducing the likelihood of training related adaptations and supporting Bhpr as an accessible and simple intervention for autonomic modulation.

Despite notable improvements in observed parasympathetic markers (RMSSD, pNN50, HFms²) and overall autonomic balance (LF/HF), frequency-domain indices require cautious interpretation because respiratory rate was uncontrolled, and these parameters are sensitive to breathing patterns.(Billman, 2013)

Conclusion:

A single 15-minute session of Bhpr can produce an acute reduction in SBP and enhance overall HRV in healthy, yoga naïve adults. These results position Bhpr as a simple, accessible, and non-pharmacological method for short term autonomic modulation. Although, the magnitude of immediate effects is modest, their physiological trend is favourable, supporting further investigation on Bhpr as a scalable adjunct for cardiovascular risk reduction and autonomic health promotion.

Limitations: Since participants were unfamiliar with the procedure, variations in technique and breathing consistency may have influenced the observed outcomes. Studies involving both sexes can be useful for accounting for hormonal fluctuations and physiological differences. Extending this work to populations with cardiovascular risk factors or autonomic dysregulation (e.g., hypertension, anxiety disorders etc.) would enhance clinical relevance.

Conflict of Interest: Nil

Informed Consent: Taken from all participants.

Funding: Nil

Author's Contribution:

Anushree Rai: Conceptualization, Literature Search, Data Collection, Manuscript Writing

Hirok Chakraborty: Conceptualization, Study Design, Data Collection, Manuscript Writing

Vinay AV: Literature Search, Data Collection Tool development, Manuscript Review

Sindhu R: Literature Search, Methodology, Manuscript Review

Ratnesh Sinha: Study Design, Methodology, Data Analysis, Manuscript Writing

Data Availability: The data that support the findings of this study will be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethical Statement: The study was conducted after getting ethical clearance from the Kasturba Medical College and Kasturba Hospital Ethical Committee (IEC2: 299/2022) dated 18th October 2022.

Reference:

- Aftyka, J., Staszewski, J., Dębiec, A., Pogoda-Wesołowska, A., & Żebrowski, J. (2023). Heart rate variability as a predictor of stroke course, functional outcome, and medical complications: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Physiology, 14*, 1115164.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1115164>
- Arakaki, X., Arechavala, R. J., Choy, E. H., Bautista, J., Bliss, B., Molloy, C., Wu, D.-A., Shimojo, S., Jiang, Y., Kleinman, M. T., & Kloner, R. A. (2023). The connection between heart rate variability (HRV), neurological health, and cognition: A literature review. *Frontiers in Neuroscience, 17*, 1055445. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2023.1055445>
- Behera, S. K., Das, S., Xavier, A. S., Selvarajan, S., & Anandabaskar, N. (2019). Indian Council of Medical Research's National Ethical Guidelines for biomedical and health research involving human participants: The way forward from 2006 to 2017. *Perspectives in Clinical Research, 10*(3), 108. https://doi.org/10.4103/picr.PICR_10_18
- Billman, G. E. (2013). The LF/HF ratio does not accurately measure cardiac sympatho-vagal balance. *Frontiers in Physiology, 4*, 26. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2013.00026>
- Blaser, B. L., Weymar, M., & Wendt, J. (2023). The effect of a single-session heart rate variability biofeedback on attentional control: Does stress matter? *Frontiers in Psychology, 14*.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1292983>
- Chetry, D., Chhetri, A., Rajak, D. K., Rathore, V., & Gupta, A. (2024). Exploring the health benefits of bhramari pranayama (humming bee breathing): A comprehensive literature review. *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology, 68*(1), 71–85.
https://doi.org/10.25259/IJPP_325_2023

- Gobel, F. L., Norstrom, L. A., Nelson, R. R., Jorgensen, C. R., & Wang, Y. (1978). The rate-pressure product as an index of myocardial oxygen consumption during exercise in patients with angina pectoris. *Circulation*, *57*(3), 549–556. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.57.3.549>
- Goldstein, D. S., Benthoo, O., Park, M.-Y., & Sharabi, Y. (2011). Low-frequency power of heart rate variability is not a measure of cardiac sympathetic tone but may be a measure of modulation of cardiac autonomic outflows by baroreflexes. *Experimental Physiology*, *96*(12), 1255–1261. <https://doi.org/10.1113/expphysiol.2010.056259>
- Hellmann, F., Marceau, E., & Cruz, R. de L. (2024). 60th anniversary of the Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical challenges in the 10th amendment. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, *117*(8), 257–263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01410768241261758>
- Jerath, R., Edry, J. W., Barnes, V. A., & Jerath, V. (2006). Physiology of long pranayamic breathing: Neural respiratory elements may provide a mechanism that explains how slow deep breathing shifts the autonomic nervous system. *Medical Hypotheses*, *67*(3), 566–571. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2006.02.042>
- Kuppusamy, M., Kamaldeen, D., Pitani, R., & Amaldas, J. (2016). Immediate Effects of Bhramari Pranayama on Resting Cardiovascular Parameters in Healthy Adolescents. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research : JCDR*, *10*(5), CC17–CC19. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2016/19202.7894>
- Kuppusamy, M., Kamaldeen, D., Pitani, R., Amaldas, J., Ramasamy, P., Shanmugam, P., & Vijayakumar, V. (2020). Effects of yoga breathing practice on heart rate variability in healthy adolescents: A randomized controlled trial. *Integrative Medicine Research*, *9*(1), 28–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imr.2020.01.006>
- Laborde, S., Allen, M. S., Borges, U., Dosseville, F., Hosang, T. J., Iskra, M., Mosley, E., Salvotti, C., Spolverato, L., Zammit, N., & Javelle, F. (2022). Effects of voluntary slow breathing on heart rate and heart rate variability: A systematic review and a meta-analysis. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, *138*, 104711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104711>

- Laborde, S., Mosley, E., & Thayer, J. F. (2017). Heart Rate Variability and Cardiac Vagal Tone in Psychophysiological Research – Recommendations for Experiment Planning, Data Analysis, and Data Reporting. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00213>
- Lundberg, J. O., Settergren, G., Gelinder, S., Lundberg, J. M., Alving, K., & Weitzberg, E. (1996). Inhalation of nasally derived nitric oxide modulates pulmonary function in humans. *Acta Physiologica Scandinavica*, 158(4), 343–347. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-201X.1996.557321000.x>
- Malik, M. (1996). Heart rate variability: Standards of measurement, physiological interpretation and clinical use. Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and the North American Society of Pacing and Electrophysiology. *Circulation*, 93(5), 1043–1065.
- McCraty, R., & Shaffer, F. (2015). Heart Rate Variability: New Perspectives on Physiological Mechanisms, Assessment of Self-regulatory Capacity, and Health risk. *Global Advances in Health and Medicine*, 4(1), 46–61. <https://doi.org/10.7453/gahmj.2014.073>
- Mooventhan, A., & Khode, V. (2014). Effect of Bhramari pranayama and OM chanting on pulmonary function in healthy individuals: A prospective randomized control trial. *International Journal of Yoga*, 7(2), 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-6131.133875>
- Muralikrishnan, K., Balakrishnan, B., Balasubramanian, K., & Visnegarawla, F. (2012). Measurement of the effect of Isha Yoga on cardiac autonomic nervous system using short-term heart rate variability. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 3(2), 91–96. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-9476.96528>
- Nivethitha, L., Manjunath, N. K., & Mooventhan, A. (2017). Heart Rate Variability Changes During and after the Practice of Bhramari Pranayama. *International Journal of Yoga*, 10(2), 99–102. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-6131.205518>
- Pramanik, T., Pudasaini, B., & Prajapati, R. (2010). Immediate effect of a slow pace breathing exercise Bhramari pranayama on blood pressure and heart rate. *Nepal Medical College Journal: NMJ*, 12(3), 154–157.

- Rajendra Acharya, U., Paul Joseph, K., Kannathal, N., Lim, C. M., & Suri, J. S. (2006). Heart rate variability: A review. *Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing*, 44(12), 1031–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11517-006-0119-0>
- Saoji, A. A., Raghavendra, B. R., & Manjunath, N. K. (2019). Effects of yogic breath regulation: A narrative review of scientific evidence. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 10(1), 50–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaim.2017.07.008>
- Sathe, S., Thodge, K., Rajandekar, T., & Agrawal, A. (2020). To Find Out Immediate Effect of Bhramari Pranayama on Blood Pressure, Heart Rate and Oxygen Saturation in Hypertensive Patients. *International Journal of Current Research and Review*, 12, 193–197. <https://doi.org/10.31782/IJCRR.2020.121919>
- Sevoz-Couche, C., & Laborde, S. (2022). Heart rate variability and slow-paced breathing: when coherence meets resonance. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, 135, 104576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104576>
- Shaffer, F., & Ginsberg, J. P. (2017). An Overview of Heart Rate Variability Metrics and Norms. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 5, 258. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00258>
- Shaffer, F., McCraty, R., & Zerr, C. L. (2014). A healthy heart is not a metronome: An integrative review of the heart's anatomy and heart rate variability. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5, 1040. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01040>
- Sharma, K., Basu-Ray, I., Sayal, N., Vora, A., Bammidi, S., Tyagi, R., Modgil, S., Bali, P., Kaur, P., Goyal, A. K., Pal, D. K., Arvind, H., Jindal, K., Garg, V., Matyal, B., Thakur, N., Chhikara, A., Kaur, N., Maanju, P., ... Anand, A. (2022). Yoga as a Preventive Intervention for Cardiovascular Diseases and Associated Comorbidities: Open-Label Single Arm Study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 843134. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.843134>
- Shetty, S. P., Patil, A. V., Khodnapur, J. P., Kotennavar, M., Jaju, P., Savanth, M., Ghanteppagol, V., Ballal, N., Gb, D., & Doddannavar, S. (2024). The Impact of Bhramari Pranayama and Om Chanting on Post-operative Wound Healing: A Focus on the Nitric Oxide Pathway. *Cureus*, 16(11), e73511. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.73511>

Singh, N. (2014). *Sample Size Calculator for Estimating a Proportion*.

<https://statulator.com/SampleSize/ss1P.html>

Sujie, M., Kaiwen, X., Hong, X., & Xiujin, G. (2024). The impact of traditional mind–body exercises on pulmonary function, exercise capacity, and quality of life in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Frontiers in Medicine*, *11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1359347>

Telles, S., Singh, N., & Balkrishna, A. (2012). Managing Mental Health Disorders Resulting from Trauma through Yoga: A Review. *Depression Research and Treatment*, *2012*, 401513. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/401513>

Thayer, J. F., Ahs, F., Fredrikson, M., Sollers, J. J., & Wager, T. D. (2012). A meta-analysis of heart rate variability and neuroimaging studies: Implications for heart rate variability as a marker of stress and health. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, *36*(2), 747–756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2011.11.009>

Trivedi, G., Sharma, K., Saboo, B., Kathirvel, S., Konat, A., Zapadia, V., Prajapati, P. J., Benani, U., Patel, K., & Shah, S. (2023). Humming (Simple Bhramari Pranayama) as a Stress Buster: A Holter-Based Study to Analyze Heart Rate Variability (HRV) Parameters During Bhramari, Physical Activity, Emotional Stress, and Sleep. *Cureus*, *15*(4), e37527. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.37527>

Tyagi, A., & Cohen, M. (2016). Yoga and heart rate variability: A comprehensive review of the literature. *International Journal of Yoga*, *9*(2), 97–113. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-6131.183712>

Ushamohan, B. P., Belur, Y. K., Rajasekaran, A. K., Ilavarasu, J., & Srinivasan, T. M. (2023). A Framework of Measurable Features of Bhramari Pranayama Leading to Meditation. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, *16*(4), 259–265. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i4.752>

Vinay, A., Venkatesh, D., & Ambarish, V. (2016). Impact of short-term practice of yoga on heart rate variability. *International Journal of Yoga*, *9*(1), 62–66. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-6131.171714>